

1 **Well-Tempered MCMC simulations for population**
2 **pharmacokinetic models**

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17 **Abstract**

18 A full Bayesian statistical treatment of complex pharmacokinetic or pharmacodynamic
19 models, in particular in a population context, gives access to powerful inference, including on
20 model structure. Markov Chain Monte Carlo (MCMC) samplers are typically used to
21 estimate the joint posterior parameter distribution of interest. Among MCMC samplers, the
22 simulated tempering algorithm (TMCMC) has a number of advantages : it can sample from
23 sharp multi-modal posteriors; it provides insight into identifiability issues useful for model
24 simplification; it can be used to compute accurate Bayes factors for model choice; the
25 simulated Markov chains mix quickly and have assured convergence in certain conditions.
26 The main challenge when implementing this approach is to find an adequate scale of
27 auxiliary inverse temperatures (perks) and associated scaling constants. We solved that
28 problem by adaptive stochastic optimization and describe our implementation of TMCMC
29 sampling in the *GNU MCSim* software. Once a grid of perks is obtained, it is easy to perform
30 posterior-tempered MCMC sampling or likelihood-tempered MCMC (thermodynamic
31 integration, which bridges the joint prior and the posterior parameter distributions, with
32 assured convergence of a single sampling chain). We compare TMCMC to other samplers

33 and demonstrate its efficient sampling of multi-modal posteriors and calculation of Bayes
34 factors in two stylized case-studies and two realistic population pharmacokinetic inference
35 problems, one of them involving a large PBPK model.

36 **1 Introduction**

37 In modeling pharmacokinetics and pharmacodynamics, a Bayesian statistical framework
38 gives access to a range of flexible inference options, including hierarchical non-conjugate
39 models for population modeling (Damien et al. 1999; Gelman 2006) or seamless integration
40 of prior and sequential knowledge. The incorporation of prior knowledge is particularly
41 important in mechanistic modeling such as physiologically-based pharmacokinetic (PBPK)
42 models (Gelman et al. 1996; Langdon et al. 2007; Tsamandouras et al. 2013; Zhang et al.
43 2011) or systems biology models (Bois 2009; Hamon et al. 2014). The development of
44 powerful numerical Markov chain Monte Carlo (MCMC) algorithms (Girolami and
45 Calderhead 2011; Robert and Casella 2011) has fueled the increasing use of Bayesian
46 methods. However, those algorithms are still very computationally intensive and for complex
47 models or large datasets can take hours or days to reach convergence on current computers
48 (Hsieh et al. 2018). The problem is compounded by the fact that, in most cases, convergence
49 should be assessed by running multiple simulated Markov chains (Gelman and Rubin 1992).

50 The tempered MCMC algorithm and its siblings, akin to simulated annealing (Geyer and
51 Thompson 1995; Marinari and Parisi 1992), have the potential to dramatically improve this
52 picture. In simulated tempering MCMC, the sampled posterior density (or just the data
53 likelihood, in the so-called thermodynamic integration, TI, variant) is raised to a series of
54 powers (inverse-temperatures, or perks) ranging from 0 to 1. At perk 0, the sampling density
55 is uniform (or is equal to the prior in TI), and perk 1 corresponds to the target joint posterior
56 distribution. The perk is treated as an auxiliary variable, sampled randomly along a discrete
57 grid of values, so that the simulated Markov chain explores the whole parameter space over a
58 series of powered posteriors.

59 This algorithm has good mixing properties and can deal with difficult or even multi-modal
60 posteriors, as will be shown in this paper, because the set of powered distributions provides a
61 smooth landscape that a Markov chain can efficiently explore. This translates into rapid
62 convergence, and, if perk zero is reached, the chain renews and convergence is guaranteed
63 with only a single chain being run (Geyer and Thompson 1995; Robert and Casella 2011).
64 Reaching power zero also provides, at no extra computation cost, an estimate of the
65 integrated data likelihood (the posterior normalization constant), which in turn can be used to
66 compute Bayes factors enabling statistical testing of model structure (Calderhead and
67 Girolami 2009; Friel and Wyse 2012; Geyer and Thompson 1995). To date, validation of this
68 method has been confined to limited datasets and simple models, because setting adequate
69 perk values in simulated tempering MCMC for complex or differential models has proved to
70 be very difficult (Behrens et al. 2012).

71 We developed and implemented a new automatic perk grid setting algorithm which leads to a
72 fully operational simulated tempering MCMC algorithm. We demonstrate its capabilities, in
73 its TI variant, for the Bayesian calibration of population pharmacokinetic (PK) models of

74 various complexity, using previously published PK models and data on theophylline and
75 acetaminophen as test cases. We start by illustrating the advantages of TI with two simple
76 inference problems, one of which has an analytical solution.

77 2 Materials and Methods

78 2.1 Simulated tempering MCMC Approach and Algorithms

79 Standard Metropolis-Hasting MCMC typically proceeds from one iteration to the next by
80 sampling a proposed value, θ' , for a parameter of interest from a (typically) Normal kernel
81 distribution $G(\cdot)$ centered on the current value of the parameter, θ . The current value has a
82 given probability density, $P(\theta)$, under the prior distribution and the proposed value has prior
83 density $P(\theta')$. The density of θ' under the Normal kernel centered at θ will be noted $G(\theta'|\theta)$
84 and the density of θ under the Normal kernel centered at θ' will be noted
85 $G(\theta|\theta')$. All model predictions that depend on parameter θ are recomputed and the likelihood
86 of the data D , $P(D|\theta')$, is evaluated numerically up to an unknown constant, $P(D)$. The data
87 likelihood given θ , $P(D|\theta)$, has been recorded previously. It can be shown (*e.g.*, Roberts and
88 Smith 1994) that if θ' is accepted (and becomes the current value for the next step) with
89 probability

$$90 \quad r = \min\left(\frac{P(\theta') \cdot P(D|\theta') \cdot G(\theta|\theta')}{P(\theta) \cdot P(D|\theta) \cdot G(\theta'|\theta)}, 1\right) \quad (1)$$

91 then the Markov chain converges in distribution to the posterior distribution of θ , $P(\theta) \times P(D|$
92 $\theta)$. The unknown constant $P(D)$ cancels out between the numerator and the denominator of
93 Eq. 1. If the proposed value is not accepted, the value θ is kept (and becomes repeated in the
94 simulated chain). When several parameters need to be sampled, it is sufficient to update them
95 sequentially. In that case, the simulated chain converges to the joint posterior distribution of
96 all parameters. The proposal kernel needs to be tuned so that jumps are large enough so that
97 the simulated chain moves rapidly in the entire posterior distribution, but not too large,
98 because too many samples would be rejected, leading to a non-moving chain (Roberts et al.
99 1997). The convergence of the simulated chain to the posterior distribution needs to be
100 checked systematically, preferably by running several chains for long enough (Gelman and
101 Rubin 1992). A sufficient number (typically thousands) of sampled parameter values or
102 parameter vectors also need to be collected to form useful summaries, such as percentiles of
103 their posterior distribution. Several algorithms, for example Hamiltonian MCMC (Girolami
104 and Calderhead 2011), optimize the proposal mechanism and offer convergence in fewer
105 iterations, albeit with a higher computation cost per iteration.

106 By contrast, in simulated tempering MCMC, a series of m perks λ values (inverse-
107 temperatures, usually between 0 and 1) is defined and applied as a power either to the
108 posterior distribution, in posterior-tempered MCMC, or to the data likelihood in the case of
109 TI. The perk λ is an auxiliary parameter that is also randomly sampled, but from a discrete set
110 of values, moving up or down one value at a time (Geyer and Thompson 1995). For a given

111 perk λ , the acceptance probabilities r_{pt} and r_{ti} for posterior-tempered MCMC and TI are,
 112 respectively

$$113 \quad r_{pt} = \min \left(\left[\frac{P(\theta') \cdot P(D|\theta')}{P(\theta) \cdot P(D|\theta)} \right]^\lambda \cdot \frac{G(\theta|\theta')}{G(\theta'|\theta)}, 1 \right) \quad (2)$$

114 for posterior-tempered MCMC, and

$$115 \quad r_{ti} = \min \left(\frac{P(\theta')}{P(\theta)} \cdot \left[\frac{P(D|\theta')}{P(D|\theta)} \right]^\lambda \cdot \frac{G(\theta|\theta')}{G(\theta'|\theta)}, 1 \right) \quad (3)$$

116 for TI. If λ equals 1, Eqs. 2 and 3 are identical to Eq. 1, and the θ samples are drawn from
 117 their posterior (target) distribution (the “cold” distribution in Geyer and Thompson’s paper).
 118 When λ equals zero, Eq. 2 implies sampling θ from a uniform distribution, while Eq. 3
 119 samples θ from its prior distribution (the “hot” distribution of Geyer and Thompson;
 120 incidentally, Geyer and Thompson inverted by mistake the hot and cold distributions in their
 121 paper, page 910). Other values of λ (e.g., 0.1) correspond to intermediate distributions, which
 122 are generally not of interest but are used to increase mixing of the chain. The MCMC chain
 123 resets if the θ are independently sampled at perk zero. This automatically ensures that
 124 convergence is achieved, provided that the intermediate distributions are visited regularly.
 125 The Markov chain should still be simulated for long enough to gather a sufficient number of
 126 samples from the cold distribution to permit robust inference.

127 The values of λ must be set in such a way that the sampler often jumps from between them.
 128 The jump frequency depends strongly on a series of tuning parameters (called pseudo-priors,
 129 or π in the notation of Geyer and Thompson 1995). There is one pseudo-prior π_λ for each
 130 value of λ . A pseudo-prior is proportional to the normalization constant of the posterior
 131 distribution density raised to power λ . However, those pseudo-priors cannot be determined in
 132 advance. So, there are two adjustment problems to solve: adjusting the pseudo-priors for a set
 133 of perk values λ , and adjusting those perk values.

134 Geyer and Thompson consider those two problems separately and iterate between them. For
 135 adjusting the pseudo-priors, they suggest in particular to use stochastic Robbins-Munro
 136 process (Robbins and Monro 1951) (they propose two other methods, rather impractical: the
 137 first one implies that we already have good starting values for the pseudo-priors and hence
 138 cannot be used alone; the second one starts by using a Metropolis-coupled MCMC sampler,
 139 which increases dramatically the complexity of the approach). The Robbins-Munro they
 140 propose starts with any values for the pseudo-priors (e.g., 1.0 for all) and updates them as the
 141 chain progresses. At iteration k , the amount $c_0/(m(k + n_0))$ is added to $\log(\pi_\lambda)$ for each λ not
 142 equal to the current λ , and the amount $c_0/(k + n_0)$ is subtracted from the current $\log(\pi_\lambda)$. The
 143 two positive constants c_0 and n_0 are chosen by the user. As defined above, m is the number of
 144 perks values in use.

145 For adjusting the set of perk values, Geyer and Thompson proposed to linearly interpolate the
146 cumulated values of observed transition rates between a current set of perks, and set new perk
147 values to obtain about 30% jump probabilities in the next round of adjustment. However, this
148 simple algorithm gives no indication as to what to do if all transition rates are null at the start
149 (in our hands, a frequent situation with realistic models) and tends to lead to too many perk
150 values.

151 In our approach, we continuously optimize the pseudo-priors with the Robbins-Munro
152 process suggested by Geyer and Thompson, setting c_0 and n_0 to 100. For setting the perk
153 values, we noticed that when the relationship between well-tuned log-pseudo-priors and perk
154 values is linear, jumps are easy and it is possible to reduce the number of perks. Therefore,
155 we developed the following adaptive perk setting algorithm: Briefly, in the first batch of 100
156 MCMC simulations (sampling all model parameters θ to be inferred and perks λ), only two
157 perks are used: 1.0 and 0.99. If the observed transition rate between the two perks is higher
158 than 30%, a lower perk chosen from a preset table is added to the set, and the batch size is
159 increased by 100. If the transition rate is below 30%, the lower perk is raised halfway toward
160 1.0. In both cases, a new batch is run. When more than three perks are in the grid, we check if
161 some perks can be removed. If so, the batch size is lowered by 100. The algorithm similarly
162 iterates until perk zero is reached or a preset number of MCMC iterations (currently 300,000)
163 have been run. A pseudo-code listing of the algorithm is given as Supplementary Material,
164 and the actual code is available at www.gnu.org/software/mcsim.

165 The above procedure minimizes the number of perks, optimizes their placement, and the
166 jump frequencies between them, while computing the corresponding pseudo-priors. It is also
167 possible for the user to bypass that initial phase and impose a set of predefined perks. Actual
168 simulated tempering MCMC sampling is run subsequently with the set of perk values found,
169 but the values of the pseudo-priors continue to be refined through the Robbins-Munro
170 process. The occupancy numbers o_i (number of iterations spend at each perk λ_i are also
171 recorded).

172 After running the sampler, estimating the probability of the data (integrated likelihood) given
173 the model is straightforward: This probability is also the normalization constant of the target
174 posterior density, which is inversely proportional to its pseudo-prior π_1 (Geyer and Thompson
175 1995):

$$176 \quad P_1(\mathbf{D}) = \alpha \frac{o_1}{\pi_1} \quad (4)$$

177 where o_1 is the occupancy number at perk 1 and α an unknown proportionality constant. An
178 estimate of α can be obtained at perk 0, since we also have:

$$179 \quad P_0(\mathbf{D}) = \alpha \frac{o_0}{\pi_0} \quad (5)$$

180 However, at perk 0 the posterior distribution is equal to the prior and $P_0(\mathbf{D})$ can be evaluated
 181 numerically (the prior is user-specified and needs to be evaluated at each step of the sampler;
 182 if a normalized prior is computed $P_0(\mathbf{D})$ is equal to 1). Therefore,

$$183 \quad P_1(\mathbf{D}) = P_0(\mathbf{D}) \frac{\pi_0 \sigma_1}{\pi_1 \sigma_0} \quad (6)$$

184 The normalized posterior parameter density can now be computed from the eventually
 185 unnormalized prior and likelihood:

$$186 \quad P_1(\boldsymbol{\theta} | \mathbf{D}) = \frac{P_1(\boldsymbol{\theta}) \cdot P_1(\mathbf{D} | \boldsymbol{\theta})}{P_1(\mathbf{D})} \quad (7)$$

187 Comparing two models A and B amounts to calculating $P_1(\mathbf{D})$ for each and forming the Bayes
 188 factor for A over B . If we denote by $P_1(\mathbf{D} | A)$ the integrated likelihood of model A and
 189 $P_1(\mathbf{D} | B)$ that for model B , the Bayes factor B_{AB} is simply $P_1(\mathbf{D} | A)$ over $P_1(\mathbf{D} | B)$. Values of
 190 B_{AB} higher than 1 indicated that model A should be favored (Calderhead and Girolami 2009).

191 2.2 Multi-modal posterior test case

192 Multi-modal posteriors are a challenge in MCMC sampling and can be found in
 193 pharmacometrics. A well-known example is the flip-flop phenomenon (Yáñez et al. 2011).
 194 The theophylline test case described below also exhibits this feature (see Results, section
 195 3.3). The test case presented here is a simple Bayesian linear regression applied to an
 196 artificial dataset (see Figure 1). The data (x,y) are, in fact, a mixture of two linear
 197 components, for which we want to calibrate only one slope parameter a (data are given in
 198 Supplementary Material Table S1). There are clearly two solutions to this inference problem:
 199 a positive slope with one very small SD, σ_1 , for the part of the data that is increasing with the
 200 independent variable x , the other SD, σ_2 (for the data decreasing with x), being other very
 201 large; or a negative slope, with σ_1 small and σ_2 large. The intercept was assumed to be known
 202 and equal to zero. The data likelihood was assumed to be Normal, with mean $a \cdot x$ and SDs σ_1
 203 or σ_2 . Parameter a was assigned a uniform prior ranging from -10 to 10; σ_1 and σ_2 were
 204 assigned the same log-uniform prior ranging from 0.001 to 100.

205 2.3 Inference about a Gaussian mean test case

206 This very simple model has a known solution and will be used to illustrate the derivation of
 207 the data probability (normalization constant). The mean, μ , of 100 data points (drawn from a
 208 standard Normal distribution, see Supplementary Material Table S2) was calibrated using the
 209 exact likelihood, with a Normal prior $(0, 100)$ on μ . Given a prior mean on μ (μ_0) equal to 0, a
 210 prior precision λ_0 equal to 0.01, a true precision $\lambda_{true} = 1$, and $n = 100$ data points (whose
 211 mean was $m = -0.0631515$), the analytical posterior distribution is (Bernardo and Smith
 212 1994):

213
$$\mu \sim \text{Normal}\left(\frac{\lambda_0 \cdot \mu_0 + n \lambda_{\text{true}} \cdot m}{\lambda_0 + n \cdot \lambda_{\text{true}}}, \frac{1}{\sqrt{\lambda_0 + n \cdot \lambda_{\text{true}}}}\right) \quad (8)$$

214 **2.4. Theophylline population PK test case**

215 To demonstrate population PK modeling with a compartmental model, we used plasma
 216 theophylline concentration data from the first six subjects (labeled 1 to 6) of a study by
 217 Trembath *et al.* (1980). Briefly, six healthy subjects aged 21-36 years were administered an
 218 immediate-release dose of 190 mg theophylline; plasma theophylline concentration was
 219 followed up to 12 hours after dosing. At another occasion the same subjects received five
 220 doses of a sustained release formulation containing 190 mg theophylline, twice a day; plasma
 221 concentration was measured up to 12 hours following the first and the fifth dose. In addition,
 222 subjects 4 and 6 received five doses of a sustained release formulation containing 380 mg of
 223 theophylline, twice a day, and plasma concentrations were measured up to 12 hours following
 224 fifth dose. The few measurements with null values were considered to be missing (all data are
 225 given in Supplementary Material Table S3).

226 We used a standard two-compartment distribution model with first-order input from the gut
 227 to the central compartment (see Figure 2). The quantity of drug released in the gut lumen was
 228 modeled by a first order infusion process. Elimination was from the central compartment.
 229 The model has six parameters: three first-order rate constants (k_r for release, k_a for absorption,
 230 and k_e for excretion), two transfer rate constants between the central and peripheral
 231 compartment (k_{cp} and k_{pc}), and the volume of distribution of the central compartment (V). The
 232 model can be turned into a one-compartment model by setting k_{cp} and k_{pc} to zero. Units are
 233 hours for time, liters for volumes and μmols for quantities. Immediate release was modeled as
 234 very brief (36 seconds) zero-order infusion into the gut lumen at dosing time. Sustained drug
 235 release was modeled as a similar infusion into the “drug dose” compartment, from which it is
 236 released in the gut lumen with first-order rate k_r . We considered two different population
 237 models, described next.

238 **2.4.1 Inter-individual variability model**

239 The inter-individual variability model has two levels: individuals and population. At the
 240 individual level, the likelihood of theophylline plasma concentration data ($y_{i,k}$) for subject i at
 241 occasion j_i and time $k_{i,j}$, was assumed to be log-normal:

242
$$\log(y_{i,j,k}) \sim \text{Normal}\left(\log\left(f(D_{i,j}, \theta_i, t_{i,j,k})\right), \sigma^2\right) \quad (9)$$

243 where $f(\cdot)$ is the two-compartment model, function of theophylline dose $D_{i,j}$, of a vector θ_i of
 244 six parameters ($k_{r,i}, k_{a,i}, k_{e,i}, k_{cp,i}, k_{pc,i}, V_i$), and of time $t_{i,j,k}$; σ^2 is the experimental measurement
 245 variance (on the log scale).

246 The prior distribution of σ^2 was taken to be log-uniform, with bounds corresponding
 247 approximately to a relative error ranging from 10% to 70%:

248 $\log(\sigma^2) \sim \text{Uniform}(\log(0.01), \log(0.5))$ (10)

249 At the individual level, parameters $\theta_{i,l}$ (l ranging from 1 to 6) for a given subject i were
 250 assumed to be log-normally distributed around population geometric means μ_l , with inter-
 251 individual variance δ_l^2 (on the log scale):

252 $\log(\theta_{i,l}) \sim \text{Normal}(\log(\mu_l), \delta_l^2)$ (11)

253 The prior distributions of the six population means were log-uniform and rather vague for the
 254 release rate constant k_r (with bounds corresponding to half-times of 1 hr and 20 hr) and the
 255 absorption rate constant k_a (with bounds corresponding to half-times of 6 min and 60 min).
 256 For the other parameters, log-normal distributions were used based on published information
 257 (Mitenko and Ogilvie 1973) and truncated at +/- 2 SDs:

258
$$\begin{aligned} \log(k_r) &\sim \text{Uniform}(-3.36, -0.367) \\ \log(k_a) &\sim \text{Uniform}(-0.367, 1.94) \\ \log(V) &\sim \text{Normal}(\log(20), \log(2)) [\log(5), \log(80)] \\ \log(k_e) &\sim \text{Normal}(\log(0.26), \log(2)) [\log(0.065), \log(1.04)] \\ \log(k_{cp}) &\sim \text{Normal}(\log(1), \log(2)) [\log(0.25), \log(4)] \\ \log(k_{pc}) &\sim \text{Normal}(\log(2.6), \log(2)) [\log(0.65), \log(10.4)] \end{aligned}$$
 (12)

259 *Informative* prior distributions for the six inter-individual variances δ_l^2 (in log space) were all
 260 set to:

261 $\delta_l^2 \sim \text{Inverse-Gamma}(2.25, 0.3125)$ (13)

262 For simulations with the one-compartment model, k_{cp} , and k_{pc} were set at zero at all levels and
 263 the same priors as above were used for the other parameters.

264 2.4.2 Inter- and intra-individual variability model

265 This population model has three levels: occasions, individuals, and population. Each occasion
 266 corresponds to a dosing experiment (immediate release, sustained release, or repeated dosing
 267 at eventually two doses). At the occasion level, the likelihood of theophylline plasma
 268 concentration data ($y_{i,j,k}$) for subject i at occasion j_i and time $k_{i,j}$, was assumed to be log-
 269 normal:

270 $\log(y_{i,j,k}) \sim \text{Normal}(\log(f(D_{i,j}, \xi_{i,j}, t_{i,j,k})), \sigma^2)$ (14)

271 where ξ_{ij} is a vector of six parameters ($k_{r,ij}$, $k_{a,ij}$, $k_{e,ij}$, $k_{cp,ij}$, $k_{pc,ij}$, V_{ij}) specific to subject i and
272 occasion j ; the other symbols have the same meaning as in Eq. 9, and the prior distribution of
273 σ^2 was as in Eq. 10.

274 At the occasion level, parameters $\xi_{i,j,l}$ (l from 1 to 6) were assumed to be log-normally
275 distributed around individual geometric means $\theta_{i,l}$, with intra-individual variance φ_l^2 (on the
276 log scale):

$$277 \quad \log(\xi_{i,j,l}) \sim \text{Normal}(\log(\theta_{i,l}), \varphi_l^2) \quad (15)$$

278 The prior distributions for the six intra-individual variances φ_l^2 (in log space) were all set to
279 the informative prior

$$280 \quad \varphi_k^2 \sim \text{Inverse-Gamma}(2.25, 0.3125) \quad (16)$$

281 At the individual level, parameters $\theta_{i,l}$ were assumed to be distributed as in Eq. 11. The prior
282 distributions of the six population means and inter-individual variances were as in Eqs. 12
283 and 13, respectively.

284 Here also, for simulations with the one-compartment model, k_{cp} , and k_{pc} were set at zero at all
285 levels and the same priors as above were used for the other parameters.

286 2.5 Acetaminophen population PBPK test case

287 Pharmacokinetic data from published clinical studies on acetaminophen and its metabolites,
288 acetaminophen-sulfate and acetaminophen-glucuronide, were used for model calibration. The
289 study references, their dose levels, number of subjects and mean body mass used are given in
290 Supplementary Material Table S4. We focused on studies using single oral doses, ranging
291 from 325 mg to about 1,400 mg (20 mg/kg). Within each study, the individual subjects' data
292 were averaged. The same data were used in Hsieh *et al.* (2018). The individual study data are
293 given in Supplementary Material Tables S5 to S12.

294 For acetaminophen and its conjugated metabolites, we used a PBPK model described in
295 Zurlinden and Reifeld (2016, 2017). Model details such as structure, parameters, and state
296 variables are detailed in those publications. Briefly, the model assumes physiological blood-
297 flow limited transport. The body is subdivided into fat, muscle, liver, gastrointestinal tract
298 (GI), and kidney compartments, the remaining tissues being lumped into either a rapidly- or a
299 slowly-perfused compartment. Standard Michaelis-Menten kinetics were used to describe
300 acetaminophen glucorinidation and sulfatation in the liver. The original PBPK model was
301 able to predict the distribution of acetaminophen and its conjugates adequately. The model
302 has 44 differential equations, 18 physiological parameters, and 50 chemical-specific
303 parameters.

304 A subset of 21 chemical-specific PBPK model parameters has been previously calibrated in a
305 hierarchical framework by Zurlinden and Reisfeld (2016, 2017). The hierarchy consisted of
306 individual studies, with an overall average level above. The same framework was used by
307 Hsieh *et al.* (2018) in their sensitivity analysis of the model. Hsieh *et al.* determined that only
308 15 of the original 21 parameters calibrated by Zurlinden and Reisfeld were really influential,
309 and found another five other influential parameters worth calibrating. We calibrated here the
310 20 parameters of the updated list (see Supplementary Material Table S13).

311 At the individual study level, the likelihood of the plasma concentration data ($y_{i,j,k}$) for study i
312 at time j , and for chemical species k (acetaminophen, acetaminophen-sulfate and
313 acetaminophen-glucuronide) were assumed to be log-normal, as in Eq. 9. The prior
314 distribution of each σ_k^2 was log-uniform, as in Eq. 10.

315 At the population level, parameters $\theta_{i,l}$ (l ranging from 1 to 20) for a given subject were
316 assumed to be log-normally distributed around population geometric means μ_l , with variance
317 δ_l^2 (on the log scale), as in Eq. 11 of the theophylline model. The prior distributions of the
318 twenty population means are given in Supplementary Material Table S13. Those priors were
319 derived from literature values and assumed to be uniform or truncated log-normal
320 distributions (Zurlinden and Reisfeld 2016). We assumed that the parameters in the PBPK
321 model were *a priori* independently distributed. This assumption is unlikely to hold
322 completely. However, the most important and known dependencies between physiological
323 parameters (*e.g.*, on body mass) were modeled deterministically. For the other parameters,
324 recent work suggests that they have a minimal impact on PBPK model predictions (Ring et
325 al. 2017). The prior distributions for the twenty variances δ_l^2 were all set to the inverse-
326 Gamma distribution given in Eq. 13 above.

327 2.6 Software and Hardware

328 *GNU MCSim* version 6.1.0 (www.gnu.org/software/mcsim) (Bois 2009) was used to run the
329 models and perform MCMC sampling. *R* version 3.2.3 (www.R-project.org) (R Development
330 Core Team 2013) was used for some processing calculations and graphics. The *Stan* software
331 version 2.18.2 was used for Hamiltonian MCMC simulations for the linear regression model.
332 All simulated tempering (TI) MCMC computations were performed on a 6-core 12-threads
333 workstation equipped with Intel Xeon CPUs E5-1650 V2 clocked at 3.5 GHz. The *GNU*
334 *MCSim* and *Stan* scripts used to perform the simulations are given in Supplementary Material
335 Texts S1 to S10.

336 3 Results

337 3.1 Multi-modal posterior test case

338 First, a set of 12 values (0, 10^{-6} , 10^{-5} , 10^{-4} , 10^{-3} , 10^{-2} , 0.1, 0.2, 0.9, 0.95, 0.99, 1) of perk τ was
339 found by optimization, requiring only a fraction of a second of computing time. Following
340 that phase, one in 200 out of 10^7 thermodynamic integration samples were recorded, yielding
341 a sample of 50,000 parameter vectors (a , σ_1 , σ_2). Total run time was 1.5 minutes on a laptop

342 computer. Figure 3 displays the perks visited at each iteration. The jumps from one perk to
343 another are very frequent and the sampler is mixing very well. About 4,200 parameter vectors
344 were obtained at each perk value, with 3997 samples at perk 1, which was sufficient to draw
345 reasonably precise inference.

346 Figure 1 shows the model fit to the data at the different perks. For final fit checking and
347 parameter inference, only the fit for the target posterior distribution (at $\tau = 1$) should be used,
348 but the fits for the other perks are shown here for illustration of the method. At low values of
349 τ , the sampler explores intermediate solutions starting from a purely prior-based prediction at
350 $\tau = 0$. The bimodality of the solution is obvious at $\tau = 1$. This is reflected in the relatively
351 complex bimodality of the target posterior distribution of the estimated parameters.

352 Figure 4 shows the location of the 3997 parameter triplets (slope a , σ_1 , σ_2) sampled from their
353 joint target posterior distribution ($\tau = 1$) in the parameter space. They form two thin needles,
354 the approximate volume of which represents 6×10^{-8} percents of the volume of the prior
355 parameter space. Sampling from such a posterior is literally akin to finding needles in a
356 haystack, and jumping from one mode (needle) to the other requires a wide jump, not even in
357 the same plane, but to another one. This is made possible by the progressive smoothing of the
358 posterior as perks decrease. Supplementary Material Figures S1 to S3 show histograms of the
359 posterior samples at each of the 12 perks used. The distribution of slope a goes from uniform
360 (posterior = prior when $\tau = 0$) to symmetric bimodal, while the distributions of σ_1 and σ_2 go
361 from log-uniform to asymmetric bimodal. It would be extremely difficult to jump from the
362 prior to the target posterior, but the intermediate perks offer landing patches easier to reach.

363 Figure 5 shows the marginal target posterior distribution of the sampled value of a (imagine
364 the cube in Figure 4 being flattened by pressing the left sides against the right sides; arriving
365 at a plane, and reorienting it, we get the image in Figure 5). The two peaks are widely
366 separated (by about 2000 SDs), but still well sampled.

367 By comparison, neither standard Metropolis-Hasting MCMC nor the No-U-Turn sampler (a
368 variant of standard Hamiltonian MCMC) was able to yield samples from the full posterior
369 with only one simulated Markov chain. They remained stuck in one of the two modes for as
370 long as we could run them (over a million iterations) (data not shown). Multiple chains
371 started from uniformly sampled parameter values were able to retrieve the target multi-modal
372 posterior, but many chains were required to obtain a reliable sample with a correct sampling
373 frequency of the two modes.

374 3.2 Inference about a Gaussian mean test case

375 This problem has a known solution: the expected value of the posterior mean μ is -0.063
376 (close to the data average), and its posterior SD should be very close to 0.1 (Bernardo and
377 Smith 1994). The probability density functions of the prior and exact posterior distributions
378 of μ , shown on Supplementary Material Figure S4, were used to benchmark the results.
379 Thermodynamic integration was performed with 500,000 iterations (one in five of them was
380 recorded). Only one chain was needed, since perk zero was reached and convergence
381 guaranteed. Figure 6 shows the evolution of the perks' schedule, progressively adding or

382 removing perks during the automatic adjustment phase. The eight perks proposed ($0, 10^{-6}, 10^{-5}, 10^{-4}, 10^{-3}, 10^{-2}, 0.1, 1$) were often visited by the sampler (Figure 7). Figure 8 displays a
383 histogram of the TI sample of μ at perk 0 overlaid by the known prior density, and an overlay
384 of the corresponding log-densities. As expected, they match closely, because sampling is
385 correct and the log-densities of the sampled μ values under the prior were evaluated
386 explicitly. TI allows us (Eq. 6) to evaluate the posterior's normalization constant, which was
387 equal to $\exp(-147)$. Using this value in Eq. 7, we normalized the log-posterior density
388 recorded by *GNU MCSim* and found that it approximates very well the analytical solution
389 (Figure 9). There was a 10% difference between the exact and estimated posterior densities of
390 μ . Its best estimate was -0.0632 and its SD 0.101, as expected.
391

392 3.3 Theophylline population PK test case

393 For this relatively simple model, in the two-compartment case, a TI schedule of 18 perks,
394 including perk zero, was found in 31 minutes. One TI MCMC chain of 20000 iterations took
395 another 25 minutes to complete. The sampler jumps between perks were more difficult than
396 in the two cases described above, with occupancy numbers ranging from 839 to 1443, the
397 latter for $\tau = 1$ (Figure 10)). Reference runs of 40,000 simulations were obtained with
398 standard MCMC sampling. Each chain took 52 minutes to run (208 minutes of total
399 computing time). The convergence of four chains was achieved after 20,000 simulations and
400 one in ten of the last 20,000 iterations were kept.

401 Figure 11 shows the TI posterior fits of the inter-individual variability model for each subject.
402 The maximum posterior fit is shown, in addition to 20 random posterior fits, illustrating the
403 (low) uncertainty in the predictions (σ^2 best estimate: 0.05, so about 22% CV for residuals).
404 We obtained practically the same maximum posterior fit to the data compared to standard
405 MCMC sampling (Figure 12), just twice as fast.

406 Accounting for both inter- and intra-individual variability improved the fit, in particular for
407 repeated dosing (Figure 13). The best estimate of σ^2 became 0.02, about a 14% CV. To
408 formally test whether the improvement was significant, we computed the Bayes factor for the
409 inter- and intra-variability model (*inter+intra*) over the inter-variability alone model (*inter-*
410 *only*). According to TI, the integrated likelihood of the *intra+inter* model was $\exp(5.55)$,
411 compared to $\exp(-15.2)$ for the *inter-only* model. The corresponding Bayes factor was,
412 therefore, about 10^9 , leaving no doubt that the model including both inter- and intra-
413 individual variability is more likely, and that that intra-individual variability is important.

414 The posterior parameter samples obtained by TI were generally similar (or slightly narrower)
415 as compared to those obtained by standard Metropolis-Hastings sampling (Figures 14 and
416 15), with one major exception, apparent on Figure 16. The inter-individual variance for k_{cp}
417 was higher and much more uncertain under TI. This result was due to a *second mode*
418 identified by TI for that parameter, centered around 5.5 (Figure 17), amounting to a factor of
419 10 variation among individuals. The main mode is at 0.2, and was the only one found by
420 standard MCMC simulations. The correlation between individual k_{cp} and k_{pc} values was not
421 particularly high, but the possibility of vastly different values for k_{cp} pointed to an
422 identifiability problem with the two-compartment model.

423 This identifiability issue was confirmed by turning off the exchanges between the central and
424 peripheral compartment and calibrating the resulting one-compartment model with the
425 theophylline data. The data fits obtained are visually identical to those obtained with the two-
426 compartment model (data not shown). According to TI, the integrated likelihood of the one-
427 compartment inter- and intra-individual variability model (*intra+inter-1cpt*) was $\exp(8.73)$,
428 and $\exp(-15)$ for the one-compartment inter-individual variability model (*inter-only-1cpt*).
429 When comparing with the previous two-compartment results, when only inter-individual
430 variability is included, the one-compartment model is only marginally better than the two-
431 compartment model ($\exp(-15)$ versus $\exp(-15.2)$), or a Bayes factor of $\exp(0.2) = 1.2$). On the
432 other hand, when both inter- and intra-individual variability are included, the one-
433 compartment model is substantially favored ($\exp(8.73)$ versus $\exp(5.55)$), or a Bayes factor of
434 $\exp(3.18) = 24$). Moreover, it is clear that including both sources of variability is better
435 supported by the data. Summaries of the posterior parameter distributions for the one-
436 compartment inter- and intra-individual variability model are shown in Figure 18.

437 3.4 Acetaminophen population PBPK test case

438 The acetaminophen kinetic model is much more complex than the models tested above. For
439 reference runs with standard MCMC sampling, 10 chains (of 300,000 simulations each) were
440 needed to obtain convergence. The final sample contained 5000 parameter vectors (1 in 300
441 of the last 150,000 runs of 10 chains). Each chain took between 26 and 34 hours (average 33
442 hours) to run, amounting to 330 hours of total computing time.

443 With TI MCMC, finding an adequate TI schedule of 24 perks, including perk zero, required
444 67,000 iterations and 6 hours of computing time. An additional 100,000 iterations took 11
445 hours to complete. Individual perk visits ranged from 3059 to 4625, with 4124 at $\tau = 0$ and
446 4286 at $\tau = 1$ (see Supplementary Material Figure S5). Thus, a sample approximately
447 equivalent to the reference one was obtained in 20 times less total computation time (twice
448 less wall-clock time).

449 The maximum posterior fit obtained by TI MCMC was excellent, and equivalent to the one
450 obtained with reference MCMC (Figure 19) (see also Hsieh et al. 2018, Figure 5). The
451 posterior distributions are practically identical to those obtained by standard MCMC (Figures
452 20 and 21).

453 4 Discussion

454 We have implemented an algorithm to automatically set perk scales for simulated tempering
455 MCMC. Finding appropriate scales (including perk zero) for complex models gives access to
456 powerful Bayesian inference tools, applicable to a wide variety of complex models, including
457 population PBPK models, for example. We had previously used simulated tempering MCMC
458 in an *in vitro* PK context (Wilmes et al. 2015), but had to set the perk scale manually and did
459 not reach perk zero (the lowest perk reached was 0.15). Still, that methodology allowed good
460 mixing of the chains for an inference problem made difficult by missing and aggregated data.
461 We demonstrated here efficient Bayesian parametric inference through TI in the case of
462 complex multi-modal posteriors, and applications to model choice through Bayes factors. We
463 focused on TI in our case-studies because going from the target posterior distribution to the

464 prior is easier than going to a uniform distribution, and because it is efficient for inference,
465 since the prior is known.

466 We have shown how tempered MCMC can help detect and characterize multi-modal
467 posteriors. It would be a mistake to dismiss multi-modality as an artifact. It is very
468 informative about the behavior of the model and the information content of the data. We often
469 are blind to it because the algorithms we use get stuck in one mode, without any assurance
470 that this is the optimum. The simplified, but still computationally difficult, multi-modal
471 regression model we used in the first case-study was very efficiently solved. It is somewhat
472 contrived and abstract, but realistic models' calibration is fraught with multi-modal data
473 likelihoods (for example in the case of cyclic behaviors, for which different periods can
474 provide adequate solutions). Such problems are compounded by model imperfections, which
475 make for no unique best fit, but for a range of less-than-optimal or even bad options. A
476 concrete example of a multi-modal posterior arose in the theophylline case-study: TI
477 identified a second mode in a variance parameter. That is a bit more subtle than the well-
478 known flip-flop phenomenon. The presence of a high variability mode oriented us toward a
479 reduction in model complexity. We do not dispute that theophylline distribution in the rat or
480 human has an early fast distribution phase (Mitenko and Ogilvie 1973; Paalzow 1975);
481 however, the oral dosing data of Trembath and Boobis (1980) do not allow a proper
482 identification of transfers to a peripheral compartment, and the variability and imprecision of
483 historical data did not allow us to set a very informative prior on those parameters. Yet, it is
484 worth pointing that going from a complex model to a simpler one is a notably difficult
485 problem. TI allowed us to perform what is, in essence, a powerful posterior sensitivity
486 analysis (Gelman et al. 1996) for which detection of multi-modality was a prerequisite.
487 Alternatives such as prior-based sensitivity analysis are definitely useful (Hsieh et al. 2018;
488 Melillo et al. 2019), but they do not make full use of the data. Note also that the detection of
489 the over-parameterization was partly enabled by the hierarchical structure of the population
490 model with the intra-individual variance revealing the over-fitting.

491 The second case-study illustrated the application of TI to posterior density normalization. By
492 itself, normalization is not very useful, since Bayesian inference can be made on the basis of
493 the sampled parameter values, which do not require normalization of the posterior density to
494 be obtained. However, the posterior normalization constant can be used to choose between
495 competing models, through Bayes factors. Parsimony is favored and the models compared do
496 not need to be nested as required by traditional methods such as the likelihood ratio test. We
497 used Bayes factors to show that the theophylline dataset is much better described by a
498 population model including both intra- and inter-individual variability than by a model with
499 inter-individual variability only. In addition, for that dataset, a one-compartment model is
500 preferable to a two-compartment model (for the sake of parsimony). However, as discussed
501 above, other data may justify the use of a two-compartment model. The ability of TI variants
502 to yield estimates of normalization constants justifies the interest it is currently receiving in
503 the statistical literature (Behrens et al. 2012; Bhattacharya et al. 2019; Friel et al. 2014;
504 Miasojedow et al. 2013; Zhou et al. 2016).

505 The two population PK case-studies also show that the same or better results are obtained
506 with simulated tempering compared to those of standard Metropolis-Hasting MCMC
507 sampling, but with a lower computational burden. In the case of acetaminophen, better
508 sampling was achieved with 20 times fewer computations. However, for those two PK
509 models, the mixing of the chain across perks was less efficient than with the smaller models.

510 This applies also to HMCMC, which shows good performance in algebraic models, or
511 differential models of very low dimension. However, for PBPK models, HMCMC is
512 handicapped by the expensive gradient sensitivities that need to be computed (Tsiros et al.
513 2019). Clearly, more research should be devoted to those issues.

514 It would be interesting to investigate methods for checking convergence and quality of
515 tempered simulation chains, even when perk zero is not reached. In any case, enough
516 parameter vectors should be obtained at the target perk value (perk 1 for standard inference,
517 perks 0 and 1 if the value of the posterior normalizing constant is sought) to draw reasonably
518 precise inference. This imposes an unavoidable lower limit on the number of simulations and
519 computer time for complex models. However, it would be possible to parallelize the
520 computation of multiple TI chains after perk schedule optimization. The algorithm could stop
521 after having gathered a prescribed number of samples from the target distribution.

522 Though the methodology described here can be very effective, in some cases (not necessarily
523 complex) the scale-setting algorithm fails to reach perk zero. In the worst cases, the pseudo-
524 priors are not adjusted properly and the target temperature is rarely sampled. In our
525 experience, that seems to be linked to sudden shifts in the location of the simulated Markov
526 chain which render irrelevant the pseudo-prior estimates obtained so far. In such cases,
527 manual tuning of the perk scale seems to be the only solution currently available, suggesting
528 that further understanding of that phenomenon would be beneficial. Note also that we cannot
529 claim that our algorithm yields the optimal perk schedule. It just provides good schedules.
530 Obviously, the efficiency of the MCMC sampling is affected by the schedule obtained. A perk
531 schedule can have too many, not enough, or badly spaced perks:

532 - With too many perks, jumping probability should be high but the chain needs a longer
533 time to explore the various temperatures and reach the cold or hot distributions. Reaching
534 the cold distribution (perk 1) is needed to obtain enough samples from the target posterior
535 distribution; reaching the hottest distribution is needed for good mixing. Reaching perk
536 zero is needed for guaranteed convergence or estimation of normalization constants. There
537 will also be fewer samples in each tempered distribution. Exploration time should scale
538 approximately with the square of the number of perks, and the sampling frequency of any
539 perk should scale proportionally to that number, imposing a double penalty. In addition,
540 Robbins-Munro pseudo-priors estimates will take a longer time to stabilize.

541 - With not enough or badly spaced perks, the probability of jumps between them can
542 become extremely small and pseudo-priors may never stabilize in a reasonable time.

543 Overall, it is probably better to err on the side of too many perks. Note that the schedule can
544 also be further optimized manually if needed.

545 Arguably, the use of complex models for population PK analyses is not common and many
546 practitioners prefer minimal PK models for the sake of parsimony. Even in that case, the
547 ability of TI to provide integration constants would be of interest, although a gain in speed
548 would still be probably welcome. However, there are occurrences in which complex models
549 are useful. For example, physiological and mechanistic models are preferable when
550 extrapolating parameters obtained from animal data to humans, or for analyzing pregnancy
551 data for dose-reconstruction in epidemiological studies (Brochot et al. 2019), multi-

552 compartment gut transit models are useful for bioequivalence studies (Zhang et al. 2011),
553 systems pharmacology or toxicology models are generating a lot of interest and benefit from
554 parameter estimation (Hamon et al. 2014; Vyshemirsky and Girolami 2008). Such large
555 models include many parameters, but also benefit from a lot of prior information, which
556 requires a Bayesian framework to rigorously integrate evidence from new data (Gelman et al.
557 1996). The risk of over-fitting is real for such models, but sensitivity analysis has been shown
558 to help solve the associated identifiability issues (Hsieh et al. 2018).

559 **5 Conclusions**

560 Statistical inference for complex models has progressed dramatically since the introduction of
561 numerical Bayesian methods. However, high dimensional models and models specified by
562 differential equations remain difficult to parameterize and test in terms of goodness of fit. A
563 relatively large number of numerical methods have been proposed, but most of them were
564 tested only on simplified models and remain inaccessible to practitioners owing to the lack of
565 efficient, simple and flexible implementation. We have developed a simulated tempering
566 MCMC algorithm that is efficient, amenable to automatic tuning, and available as free
567 software. This has applications well beyond the realm of PK/PD modeling, but we expect that
568 this approach will be especially useful in parameterizing and testing population PK/PD
569 models and PBPK models, which are increasingly used in the context of population health
570 and personalized medicine.

571 **6 Nomenclature, abbreviations**

572	CV:	Coefficient of variation
573	MCMC:	Markov chain Monte Carlo
574	PBPK:	Physiologically-based pharmacokinetic
575	PK:	Pharmacokinetic
576	SD:	Standard deviation
577	TI:	Thermodynamic integration

578 **7 Conflict of interest**

579 The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or
580 financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest. FB is
581 currently employed by the CERTARA company, but was not when this work was conducted.

582 **8 Author Contributions**

583 FB, N-HH, WG, BR, and WC are listed as authors. FB conceived the overall research
584 concept and design, had overall responsibility for its implementation, and performed most
585 analyses, simulations, and their interpretation. N-HH and WC contributed to the theophylline
586 and acetaminophen case studies. WG ran the Hamiltonian MCMC simulations. BR provided
587 the original acetaminophen PBPK model and data. All authors reviewed the manuscript and
588 revised it critically.

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596 **11 Data availability statement**

597 Models' code and simulation files are freely available from the official web page of *GNU*
598 *MCSim* (www.gnu.org/software/mcsim).

599 11 Supplementary Material

600 The Supplementary Material for this article can be found online.

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703

704 Figure Captions

705 **Figure 1.** Artificial data (black dots) and posterior fits (lines) of the linear regression model
706 at the different perks (inverse temperatures). The solution is clearly bimodal.

707 **Figure 2.** Two-compartment distribution model used for theophylline. Symbols are given in
708 the text.

709 **Figure 3.** Perks values sampled as a function of the TI MCMC sampler iteration in the case
710 of the linear regression model.

711 **Figure 4.** Three-dimensional plot of the positions of the 3997 parameter triplets (slope
712 a , σ_1 , σ_2) sampled from their joint target posterior distribution (perk = 1) in the parameter
713 space of the linear regression model. They align along two thin needles and individual points
714 are not discernable. Only a fraction (2.25%) of the prior parameter space is shown.

715 **Figure 5.** Marginal target posterior distribution of the sampled values of slope a in the linear
716 regression model. The two peaks are separated by a distance equal to about 600 times their
717 width.

718 **Figure 6.** Evolution of perks and associated pseudo-priors in the Gaussian inference problem
719 at the various steps of the automatic perk scale adjustment. The scale was refined until perk
720 zero was reached.

721 **Figure 7.** Perks values sampled as a function of the TI MCMC sampler iteration in the
722 Gaussian inference problem.

723 **Figure 8.** Top: Histogram of the TI MCMC sampled values of mean μ , at perk 0, in the
724 Gaussian inference problem, overlaid by the known prior density (red line). Bottom: log-
725 density of the same sample (crosses) and of the prior (red line).

726 **Figure 9.** Top: Histogram of the TI MCMC sampled values of mean μ , at perk 1, in the
727 Gaussian inference problem, overlaid by the known posterior density (red line). Bottom: log-
728 density of the same sample, normalized by the integrated likelihood (crosses) and of the exact
729 posterior (red line).

730 **Figure 10.** Perks values sampled as a function of the TI MCMC sampler iteration in the case
731 of the theophylline two-compartment population PK model.

732 **Figure 11.** Posterior fits of the two-compartment inter-individual variability population
733 model to data on plasma theophylline concentration in six subjects (Trembath and Boobis
734 1980). Red line: maximum posterior predictions. Grey lines: 20 random posterior fits.
735 Subjects (S1 to S6) are suffixed with the type of dosing: “*i*” means immediate release, “*s*”
736 sustained release, “*sr*” sustained release repeated dosing, “*srh*” *idem* with a dose twice as
737 high.

738 **Figure 12.** Observed data values vs. maximum posterior inter-individual variability model
739 predictions for the theophylline data set, in the case of either standard or TI MCMC
740 simulations, with the two-compartment inter-individual variability model.

741 **Figure 13.** Posterior fits of the two-compartment inter- and intra-individual variability
742 population model to data on plasma theophylline concentration in six subjects (Trembath and
743 Boobis 1980). Red line: maximum posterior predictions. Grey lines: 20 random posterior fits.
744 Subjects (S1 to S6) are suffixed with the type of dosing: “i” means immediate release, “s”
745 sustained release, “sr” sustained release repeated dosing, “srh” *idem* with a dose twice as
746 high.

747 **Figure 14.** Violin plots of theophylline posterior distributions of (A) population means μ , (B)
748 inter-individual variances δ^2 and residual variance σ^2 , for the two-compartment inter-
749 individual variability model. For each parameter, the left sample (white) was obtained by TI
750 MCMC simulations, and the right sample (gray) was obtained by standard MCMC
751 simulations.

752 **Figure 15.** Violin plots of theophylline individual parameters θ posterior distributions
753 (subjects S1 to S6), for the two-compartment inter-individual variability model. For each
754 subject, the parameters are respectively: k_r , k_a , V , k_e , k_{cp} , and k_{pc} . For each parameter, the left
755 sample (white) was obtained by TI MCMC simulations, and the right sample (gray) was
756 obtained by standard MCMC simulations.

757 **Figure 16.** Standard MCMC vs. TI summaries (mean \pm SD) of the posterior parameter
758 distributions for the inter-individual variability model of theophylline pharmacokinetics.
759 Colors code for population means (μ), population variances (Σ^2), residual variance (σ^2) and
760 individual parameter values (θ_i). The non-matching parameter is Σ^2 for k_{cp} .

761 **Figure 17.** Histograms of the posterior distribution of the inter-individual variance of k_{cp} , for
762 the theophylline two-compartment inter-individual variability model. Panel A: parameter
763 sample obtained by TI MCMC simulations; panel B: sample obtained by standard MCMC
764 simulations.

765 **Figure 18.** Violin plots of theophylline posterior distributions of the one-compartment model
766 with inter- and intra-individual variability. Panel A: population means μ , inter-individual
767 variances δ^2 , intra-individual variances ϕ^2 and residual variance σ^2 . Panel B: subjects' means
768 ξ . For each subject the parameters are respectively: k_r , k_a , V , and k_e . The parameter samples
769 were obtained by TI MCMC simulations.

770 **Figure 19.** Observed data values vs. maximum posterior model predictions for the
771 acetaminophen data set, in the case of either standard or TI MCMC simulations.

772 **Figure 20.** Violin plots of acetaminophen posterior parameter distributions. Panel A:
773 population means μ . Panel B: inter-individual variances δ^2 and residual variances σ^2 . For each
774 parameter, the left sample (white) was obtained by TI MCMC simulations, and the right
775 sample (gray) was obtained by standard MCMC simulations. Parameter indexing is specified
776 in Supplementary Material Table S13.

777 **Figure 21.** Boxplots of acetaminophen individual PBPK parameters θ posterior distributions
778 (subjects S1 to S8). For each subject the parameters are in the same order as in Table S2
779 above. Panel A: parameter sample obtained by TI MCMC simulations; panel B: sample
780 obtained by standard MCMC simulations.

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Figure 1. Artificial data (black dots) and posterior fits (lines) of the linear regression model at the different perks (inverse temperatures). The solution is clearly bimodal.

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Figure 2. Two-compartment distribution model used for theophylline. Symbols

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are given in the text.

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Figure 3. Perks values sampled as a function of the TI MCMC sampler iteration

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in the case of the linear regression model.

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Figure 4. Three-dimensional plot of the positions of the 3997 parameter triplets (slope a , σ_1 , σ_2) sampled from their joint target posterior distribution ($\text{perk} = 1$) in the parameter space of the linear regression model. They align along two thin needles and individual points are not discernable. Only a fraction (2.25%) of the prior parameter space is shown.

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Figure 5. Marginal target posterior distribution of the sampled values of slope a in the linear regression model. The two peaks are separated by a distance equal to about 600 times their width.

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Figure 6. Evolution of perks and associated pseudo-priors in the Gaussian inference problem at the various steps of the automatic perk scale adjustment. The scale was refined until perk zero was reached.

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Figure 7. Perks values sampled as a function of the TI MCMC sampler iteration

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in the Gaussian inference problem.

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809 **Figure 8.** Top: Histogram of the TI MCMC sampled values of mean μ , at perk 0,
 810 in the Gaussian inference problem, overlaid by the known prior density (red line).

811 Bottom: log-density of the same sample (crosses) and of the prior (red line).

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813 **Figure 9.** Top: Histogram of the TI MCMC sampled values of mean μ , at perk 1,
 814 in the Gaussian inference problem, overlaid by the known posterior density (red
 815 line). Bottom: log-density of the same sample, normalized by the integrated
 816 likelihood (crosses) and of the exact posterior (red line).

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Figure 10. Perks values sampled as a function of the TI MCMC sampler iteration

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in the case of the theophylline two-compartment population PK model.

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Figure 11. Posterior fits of the two-compartment inter-individual variability population model to data on plasma theophylline concentration in six subjects (Trembath and Boobis 1980). Red line: maximum posterior predictions. Grey lines: 20 random posterior fits. Subjects (S1 to S6) are suffixed with the type of dosing: “i” means immediate release, “s” sustained release, “sr” sustained release repeated dosing, “srh” *idem* with a dose twice as high.

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Figure 12. Observed data values vs. maximum posterior inter-individual variability model predictions for the theophylline data set, in the case of either standard or TI MCMC simulations, with the two-compartment inter-individual variability model.

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Figure 13. Posterior fits of the two-compartment inter- and intra-individual variability population model to data on plasma theophylline concentration in six subjects (Trembath and Boobis 1980). Red line: maximum posterior predictions. Grey lines: 20 random posterior fits. Subjects (S1 to S6) are suffixed with the type of dosing: “i” means immediate release, “s” sustained release, “sr” sustained release repeated dosing, “srh” *idem* with a dose twice as high.

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Figure 14. Violin plots of theophylline posterior distributions of (A) population means μ , (B) inter-individual variances δ^2 and residual variance σ^2 , for the two-compartment inter-individual variability model. For each parameter, the left sample (white) was obtained by TI MCMC simulations, and the right sample (gray) was obtained by standard MCMC simulations.

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Figure 15. Violin plots of theophylline individual parameters θ posterior distributions (subjects S1 to S6), for the two-compartment inter-individual variability model. For each subject, the parameters are respectively: k_r , k_a , V , k_e , k_{cp} , and k_{pc} . For each parameter, the left sample (white) was obtained by TI MCMC simulations, and the right sample (gray) was obtained by standard MCMC simulations.

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Figure 16. Standard MCMC vs. TI summaries (mean \pm SD) of the posterior parameter distributions for the inter-individual variability model of theophylline pharmacokinetics. Colors code for population means (μ), population variances (Σ^2), residual variance (σ^2) and individual parameter values (θ_i). The non-matching

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parameter is Σ^2 for k_{cp} .

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858 **Figure 17.** Histograms of the posterior distribution of the inter-individual variance
 859 of k_{cp} , for the theophylline two-compartment inter-individual variability model.
 860 Panel A: parameter sample obtained by TI MCMC simulations; panel B: sample
 861 obtained by standard MCMC simulations.

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Figure 18. Violin plots of theophylline posterior distributions of the one-compartment model with inter- and intra-individual variability. Panel A: population means μ , inter-individual variances δ^2 , intra-individual variances ϕ^2 and residual variance σ^2 . Panel B: subjects' means ξ . For each subject the parameters are respectively: k_r , k_a , V , and k_e . The parameter samples were obtained by TI MCMC simulations.

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Figure 19. Observed data values vs. maximum posterior model predictions for the

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acetaminophen data set, in the case of either standard or TI MCMC simulations.

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Figure 20. Violin plots of acetaminophen posterior parameter distributions. Panel A: population means μ . Panel B: inter-individual variances δ^2 and residual variances σ^2 . For each parameter, the left sample (white) was obtained by TI MCMC simulations, and the right sample (gray) was obtained by standard MCMC simulations. Parameter indexing is specified in Supplementary Material Table S13.

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Figure 21. Violin plots of acetaminophen individual PBPK parameters θ posterior distributions (subjects S1 to S8). For each subject the parameters are in the same order as in Supplementary Material Table S13. For each parameter, the left sample (red) was obtained by TI MCMC simulations, and the right sample (gray) was obtained by standard MCMC simulations.